

3D Mathcad Simulation of Photovoltage in C-Si Solar Cells Under Multispectral Illumination: Combined Effect of Transverse Magnetic Field and Base Thickness

Moussa Toure¹, Mamadou Lamine Samb^{1*}, Aly Toure¹, Youssou Gning¹, Mouhamadou Sam¹, Fatma Sow¹, Alioune Ngom¹, Ahmed Mohamed-Yahya²

¹Department of Physics and Chemistry, University Iba Der Thiam of Thies, Thies, Senegal

²Applied Research Unit for Renewable Energies, University of Nouakchott, Nouakchott, Mauritania

*mlsamb@univ-thies.sn

ABSTRACT

This study investigates the influence of an external magnetic field on the photovoltage of bifacial polycrystalline silicon photovoltaic (PV) cells with varying base thicknesses, under different illumination conditions (front-side, rear-side, and simultaneous dual-face). Numerical simulations were performed for base thicknesses ranging from 100 μm to 400 μm in 50 μm increments, considering both open-circuit and short-circuit regimes. The analysis incorporates the effect of carrier collection velocity at the p–n junction as well as constant and variable magnetic field intensities.

The results reveal that, for open-circuit conditions, the photovoltage generally increases slightly with magnetic field intensity, at a rate of approximately 10 mV per decade, regardless of base thickness, in agreement with previous experimental and simulation studies. This enhancement is attributed to a marginal reduction in bulk recombination losses due to the Lorentz force. In contrast, under short-circuit conditions, the photovoltage decreases nearly linearly with increasing magnetic field, with similar slopes across all thicknesses, indicating a transport-dominated recombination mechanism.

For rear-side and dual-face illumination, the trends are similar, though rear-side contributions decrease with base thickness due to absorption and transport losses. The magnetic field effects are primarily linked to modifications of transport parameters such as diffusion length and diffusion coefficient, rather than purely optical effects. These findings provide insights into the interplay between magnetic fields, recombination dynamics, and illumination configuration, offering potential guidance for the design of PV devices in environments where magnetic fields are present.

Keywords: Photovoltage; Bifacial solar cell; Polycrystalline silicon; Magnetic field; Carrier collector velocity; Base thickness, Three-dimensional simulation.

INTRODUCTION

The performance of bifacial polycrystalline silicon photovoltaic (PV) cells is strongly influenced by carrier transport dynamics, which can be modified by external magnetic fields. In particular, the Lorentz force alters carrier trajectories, affecting key transport parameters such as diffusion length and diffusion coefficient. This work develops a three-dimensional columnar simulation model centered on a single grain, incorporating both geometric and physical characteristics of the solar cell under varying illumination modes: front-side, rear-side, and dual-face. The model integrates magnetic field-dependent expressions for the effective diffusion coefficient $D^*(B)$ and diffusion length $L^*(B)$, as derived from established semiconductor transport theory [1,2,3,4,5]. A range of base thicknesses (100 – 400 μm) and carrier collection velocities (CCV) at the p–n junction is examined, with the magnetic field intensity spanning $1\text{e-}4$ T to $1\text{e-}3$ T. These parameters are systematically varied to assess their combined impact on the photovoltage V_{ph} under different illumination configurations and operating regimes (open-circuit and short-circuit) [4,6,7,8,9].

Physical Model and Magnetic Parameters

Description of the Simulated Solar Cell

The study is based on a three-dimensional columnar model centered on a single grain of polycrystalline silicon. A magnetic field is applied perpendicularly to the plane of the junction, thereby altering the charge carrier transport conditions. In this context, the expressions for the diffusion coefficient $D^*(B)$ and the diffusion length $L^*(B)$ are given respectively by:

$$D^*(B) = \frac{D}{1+(\mu B)^2} \tag{1}$$

$$L^*(B) = \sqrt{D^* \cdot \tau} \tag{2}$$

where:

- 1). D : classical diffusion coefficient in the absence of a magnetic field (en $\text{cm}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$),
- 2). μ : charge carrier mobility (en $\text{cm}^2 \cdot \text{V}^{-1} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$),
- 3). B : applied magnetic field intensity (en teslas, T),
- 4). τ : average lifespan of minority shareholders (en secondes, s),

Figure 1: Simulated solar cell model.

As illustrated in the previous figures, the bifacial solar cell under investigation comprises four main functional regions:

- 1). The emitter, of n^+ type and reduced thickness (ranging from 0.5 to 1 μm), is heavily doped with donor atoms at concentrations between $1e17$ and $1e19 \text{ cm}^{-3}$. It is covered with a metal grid that ensures the collection of photogenerated carriers.
- 2). The p–n junction, also referred to as the space charge region (SCR), is located between the emitter and the base. It features a strong internal electric field that efficiently separates electron–hole pairs reaching this zone.
- 3). The base, of p-type, is lightly doped with acceptors in the range of $1e15$ to $1e17 \text{ cm}^{-3}$, and serves as the main active region for carrier generation, diffusion, and recombination. Its thickness, denoted by H , is a variable parameter in this study and ranges from 100 to 400 μm depending on the configuration.
- 4). The Back Surface Field (BSF) region, located at the rear side of the base, is heavily doped with acceptors (p^+ type) at concentrations between $1e17$ and $1e19 \text{ cm}^{-3}$. It induces an electric field oriented toward the junction, promoting the return of minority carriers generated near the back surface.

To simplify the modeling approach, the following assumptions are made:

- 1). The contribution of the emitter to the overall photocurrent generation is considered negligible compared to that of the base.
- 2). The internal crystalline electric field within the base is disregarded; only the field present across the junction is taken into account.

A three-dimensional modeling framework is adopted, in which the junction is positioned at the origin of the z -axis, and the plane containing this junction defines the origin of the (x, y) coordinate system. The base thickness H is explored as a variable parameter in the range of 100 to 400 μm .

The continuity equation governing the diffusion of minority photogenerated charge carriers in the base is as follows:

$$\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} \delta(x, y, z) + [1 + (\mu B)^2] \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2} \delta(x, y, z) + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial z^2} \delta(x, y, z) - \frac{\delta(x, y, z)}{L^{*2}} = - \frac{G(z)}{D^*} \tag{3}$$

where D^* represents the diffusion coefficient and L^* represents the diffusion length. $G(z)$ represents the generation rate, and its expression is given by the following equation (4):

$$G(z) = n \sum_{i=1}^3 a_i e^{-b_i z} \tag{4}$$

a_i and b_i are coefficients derived from the modeling of the generation rate, considering the entire solar radiation spectrum when n is equal to 1.5 AM;

Where n is the number of suns.

The general solution of this continuity equation is given by the following expression (5):

$$\delta(x, y, z) = \sum_j \sum_k Z_{j,k}(z) \cos C_j x \cos C_k(B)y \quad (5)$$

with:

$$C_k(B) = \frac{C_k}{C(B)} \quad (6)$$

The coefficients C_k and C_j are obtained from the boundary conditions at the grain boundaries as follows:

$$\left. \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \delta(x, y, z) \right|_{x=\pm \frac{g_x}{2}} = \mp \frac{S_g}{2D^*} \delta\left(\pm \frac{g_x}{2}, y, z\right) \quad (7)$$

$$\left. \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \delta(x, y, z) \right|_{y=\pm \frac{g_y}{2}} = \mp \frac{S_g}{2D^*} \delta\left(x, \pm \frac{g_y}{2}, z\right) \quad (8)$$

Where S_g represents the recombination velocity at the grain boundaries.

By solving these boundary conditions, two transcendental equations are derived from which the coefficients C_k and C_j can be determined either graphically or by using a program.

These equations are as follows:

$$\tan C_j \frac{g_x}{2} = \frac{1}{C_j} \times \frac{S_g}{2D^*} \quad (9)$$

$$\tan C_k(B) \frac{g_y}{2} = \frac{1}{C_k(B)} \times \frac{S_g}{2D^*} \quad (10)$$

By integrating the general solution into the continuity equation, we obtain:

$$\frac{\partial^2}{\partial z^2} Z_{j,k}(z) - \frac{Z_{j,k}(z)}{L_{j,k}^*} = \frac{-G(z)}{D_{j,k}^*} \quad (11)$$

With:

$$\frac{1}{L_{j,k}^*} = C_j^2 + C_k^2 + \frac{1}{L^*} \quad (12)$$

$$\frac{1}{D_{j,k}^*} = \frac{16 \sin(C_j \frac{g_x}{2}) \sin(C_k(B) \frac{g_y}{2})}{D^* [C_j g_x + \sin(C_j g_x)] [C_k(B) g_y + \sin(C_k(B) g_y)]} \quad (13)$$

$L_{j,k}^*$ and $D_{j,k}^*$ represent the effective diffusion length and the effective diffusion coefficient, respectively [10,11].

The solution to this equation (11) is:

$$Z_{j,k}(z) = A_{j,k} \sinh \frac{z}{L_{j,k}^*} + B_{j,k} \cosh \frac{z}{L_{j,k}^*} + \sum_{i=1}^3 k_i e^{-b_i z} \quad (14)$$

with:

$$k_i = -\frac{n}{D_{j,k}^*} \frac{a_i L_{j,k}^*{}^2}{b_i^2 L_{j,k}^*{}^2 - 1} \quad (15)$$

The constants $A_{j,k}$ and $B_{j,k}$ are determined from the boundary conditions at the junction and the rear surface as follows:

$$D^* \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \delta(x, y, z) = S_f \delta(x, y, z) \quad \text{for } z = 0 \quad (16)$$

$$D^* \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \delta(x, y, z) = -S_b \delta(x, y, z) \quad \text{for } z = H \quad (17)$$

Where S_f is the sum of two contributions: S_{f0} [8,12], the intrinsic recombination velocity at the junction induced by the shunt resistance, and S_{fj} [8,12], which represents the current flux imposed by an external charge and defines the operating point of the cell:

$$S_f = S_{f0} + S_{fj} \quad (18)$$

S_b is the effective recombination velocity at the rear surface of the solar cell.

Evaluating the effect of an external magnetic field on the photovoltage in polycrystalline solar cells is a key step in optimizing their photovoltaic performance. Applying a magnetic field to a semiconductor alters the trajectory of charge carriers (electrons and holes) through the Lorentz force, which generally results in a reduction of their effective diffusion length [3,5,12,13]. This change directly affects the photovoltage, with the magnitude of the effect depending on both the device geometry and the illumination conditions [5,7,13].

The present simulation is based on the classical semiconductor transport equations, incorporating adjustments to the diffusion coefficient and diffusion length as functions of the magnetic field, in accordance with the models established by Sze and Ng [1], Green [2], and Schroder [6], as well as the specific magnetic transport formulations proposed by Lee et al. [8] and Wang et al. [14]. In this idealized framework, surface passivation effects are not explicitly modeled and are assumed negligible for carrier collection [7,15].

Before discussing the main simulation results, it is essential to define the magnetic field intensity range in which these effects become significant. For this purpose, Figures 2 and 3 illustrate the variation of the diffusion coefficient and the diffusion length, respectively, as functions of magnetic field intensity, enabling the identification of a relevant operating window for the subsequent simulations [3,8,13].

Figure 2: Variation of the carrier diffusion coefficient with magnetic field intensity.

The diffusion coefficient remains constant ($\approx 25 \text{ cm}^2/\text{s}$) for magnetic fields below 10^{-4} T . Beyond this threshold, it decreases rapidly to about $10 \text{ cm}^2/\text{s}$, indicating a significant reduction in effective mobility due to the magnetic field.

Figure 3: Evolution of the diffusion length as a function of magnetic field, for different carrier lifetimes.

The diffusion length increases with longer carrier lifetimes. However, for magnetic field values below 10^{-4} T , it remains almost unchanged. A marked decrease appears only when the field exceeds this limit, with a more pronounced impact for carriers with longer lifetimes.

These preliminary observations helped define an optimal magnetic field range, starting from 10^{-4} T , in which transport parameters exhibit marked variations. The following simulations therefore focus on the combined influence of the magnetic field and the base thickness on the photovoltage.

The choice of magnetic field intensities between 10^{-4} T and 10^{-3} T is motivated by these preliminary analyses: below 10^{-4} T , the effects on carrier transport parameters remain negligible, resulting in minimal variation in photovoltage; in contrast, within the $10^{-4} - 10^{-3} \text{ T}$ range, the influence becomes sufficiently significant to highlight the coupling between magnetic perturbations and transport phenomena. This range is thus suitable for assessing the device’s magnetic sensitivity and for anticipating potential performance degradation under realistic industrial or environmental conditions.

EXPRESSION OF THE PHOTOVOLTAGE (in V)

This section presents the analytical expressions for the photovoltage, obtained from the solution of the minority carrier continuity equation for three illumination configurations: front-side illumination, rear-side illumination, and dual-face illumination.

The general expression for the photovoltage under illumination mode $m \in \{\text{Front, Rear, Dual}\}$ is given by:

$$V_{ph_m} = V_T \ln \left(1 + \frac{1}{n_0} \int_{-\frac{g_x}{2}}^{\frac{g_x}{2}} \int_{-\frac{g_y}{2}}^{\frac{g_y}{2}} \delta_m(x, y, 0) dx dy \right) \tag{19}$$

with

$$V_T = \frac{KT}{q} \tag{20}$$

and

$$n_0 = \frac{n_i^2}{N_b} \tag{21}$$

where:

1. $V_{ph,m}$: Photovoltage for illumination mode m (in V),
2. V_T : Thermal voltage
3. K : Boltzmann constant
4. T : Absolute temperature (K)
5. q : elementary charge of the electron ($1,602.e-19$ C),
6. n_0 : Reference equilibrium minority carrier concentration (cm^{-3}),
7. n_i^2 : Intrinsic carrier concentration squared (cm^{-6})
8. N_b : Base doping concentration (cm^{-3})
9. D^* : effective diffusion coefficient under the influence of the magnetic field (cm^2/s),
10. g_x, g_y lateral dimensions of the simulation domain along the x and y directions (in cm),
11. $\delta_m(x, y, z)$: excess minority carrier density induced by optical generation for mode m,
12. $\left[\frac{\partial}{\partial z} \delta_m\right]_{z=0}$: derivative of the excess carrier density evaluated at the junction plane ($z = 0$).

Front-side Illumination

In this configuration, the incident photons are predominantly absorbed near the upper surface, in close proximity to the junction, which promotes efficient carrier collection. The corresponding photovoltage is expressed as:

$$V_{ph_{front}} = V_T \ln \left(1 + \frac{1}{n_0} \sum_j \sum_k (B_{frontj,k} + \sum_{i=1}^3 k_i) \times \frac{4 \sin(C_j \frac{g_x}{2}) \sin(C_k(B) \frac{g_y}{2})}{C_j C_k(B)} \right) \quad (22)$$

with:

- 1). $C_j, C_k(B)$: spectral coefficients determined by the boundary conditions in x and y, possibly dependent on magnetic field B,
- 2). $B_{frontj,k}$: mode amplitude coefficients for front-side illumination
- 3). k_i : constant derived from the analytical solution, associated with generation and recombination mechanisms.

Rear-side Illumination

In this configuration, illumination takes place from the rear side of the cell. The photogenerated carriers must traverse a greater distance before reaching the junction, which reduces their collection probability. The corresponding expression is given by:

$$V_{ph_{rear}} = V_T \ln \left(1 + \frac{1}{n_0} \sum_j \sum_k (B_{earrj,k} + \sum_{i=1}^3 k_i e^{-b_i H}) \times \frac{4 \sin(C_j \frac{g_x}{2}) \sin(C_k(B) \frac{g_y}{2})}{C_j C_k(B)} \right) \quad (23)$$

where:

- 1). $B_{rearj,k}$: mode amplitude coefficients for rear-side illumination,
- 2). H : base thickness of the solar cell (in cm),
- 3). b_i : constant derived from the analytical solution, associated with generation and recombination mechanisms.
- 4). $e^{-b_i H}$: exponential attenuation term representing carrier recombination in deeper regions.

Dual-face Illumination

When both the front and rear surfaces are illuminated simultaneously, the resulting photovoltage is not merely the arithmetic sum of the two individual contributions. This is due to recombination effects and spatial interactions between carriers generated from each side. The corresponding expression is given by:

$$V_{ph_{dual}} = V_T \ln \left(1 + \frac{1}{n_0} \sum_j \sum_k (B_{dualj,k} + \sum_{i=1}^3 k_i (1 + e^{-b_i H})) \times \frac{4 \sin(C_j \frac{g_x}{2}) \sin(C_k(B) \frac{g_y}{2})}{C_j C_k(B)} \right) \quad (24)$$

Where:

- 1). $B_{dualj,k}$: mode amplitude coefficients under dual-face illumination,
- 2). $(1 + e^{-b_i H})$: contribution of photogenerated carriers throughout the full base thickness.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Bifacial polycrystalline silicon photovoltaic (PV) solar cells represent a major research focus. Investigating the behavior of the photovoltage in such devices under the influence of an external magnetic field is of particular interest for understanding and optimizing photovoltaic performance. The presence of a magnetic field in the environment of a PV cell can affect the photovoltage in different ways, depending on the illumination mode (front-side, rear-side, or simultaneous illumination).

Effect of the Carrier Collector Velocity on the Photovoltage of a Front-Illuminated Cell under Different Magnetic Field Intensities

Case of a cell with a 100 μm base thickness

Figure 4 presents the variation of the photovoltage V_{ph} of a bifacial polycrystalline silicon PV cell with a 100 μm base thickness, illuminated from the front side, as a function of the carrier collection velocity at the p-n junction. The analysis considers the influence of various applied magnetic field intensities.

Figure 4: Photovoltage of a 100 μm PV cell front-side illuminated as a function of the recombination velocity for different values of the magnetic field B

Figure 4 shows that the photovoltage reaches a near-maximum value, with only minimal variations, for low carrier collector velocity (CCV) values (10 to 1e3 cm/s). In this regime, the boundary condition at the p–n junction remains weakly restrictive and the quasi-Fermi level separation is primarily governed by bulk transport rather than junction extraction, leading to a low sensitivity of V_{ph} to the CCV [1, 2, 16, 17]. When the CCV exceeds 1e3 cm/s, however, V_{ph} decreases almost linearly with increasing CCV: the higher collection velocity intensifies carrier recombination at the junction, raising the effective dark saturation current J_0 and thereby compressing the photovoltage [1, 2, 16, 17].

Regarding the influence of the magnetic field, the effect remains moderate but systematic. For low CCV values, V_{ph} exhibits a slight increase as B rises, which is consistent with a Lorentz-force–induced modification of carrier trajectories that marginally reduces certain transport losses [3, 5, 8]. Conversely, for high CCV values ($> 1e3$ cm/s), increasing B produces a slight decrease in V_{ph} , attributable to the reduction of both the effective diffusion coefficient and the diffusion length under magnetic influence, which limits carrier collection in a boundary-dominated regime [3, 5, 8].

Case of a cell with a 300 μm base thickness

Figure 5 depicts the variation of the photovoltage V_{ph} of a 300 μm base photovoltaic cell, illuminated from the front side, as a function of the carrier collection velocity at the p–n junction, under the influence of various applied magnetic field intensities.

Figure 5: Photovoltage of a 300 μm PV cell front-side illuminated as a function of the recombination velocity for different values of the magnetic field B

For the 300 μm base cell, the variation of photovoltage V_{ph} with CCV under different magnetic field intensities exhibits trends very similar to those observed for the 100 μm base cell (Fig. 4).

For low CCV values (10 to 1e3 cm/s), the device operates in a regime close to open circuit, where carrier collection at the junction is minimal and photogenerated carriers accumulate near the depletion region, maximizing V_{ph} [1,2,16,17]. In this range, increasing the magnetic field slightly enhances V_{ph} , likely due to a perturbation of bulk recombination mechanisms by the Lorentz force, resulting in marginally improved carrier lifetime and transport efficiency [3,5,8].

When CCV exceeds $1e3$ cm/s, V_{ph} decreases sharply for both base thicknesses, from about 0.35 V to 0.15 V as CCV approaches $1e7$ cm/s. This quasi-linear drop corresponds to a regime close to short circuit, where rapid carrier extraction through the junction increases recombination losses and raises the effective dark saturation current J_0 , thereby compressing V_{ph} [1, 2, 10, 17]. The similar slopes and magnitudes in both curves indicate that base thickness plays a limited role in the CCV-induced photovoltage reduction under front-side illumination, suggesting that the magnetic field effect is primarily linked to optical path length and bulk recombination dynamics.

The magnetic field influence follows the same pattern for both devices: negligible to slightly positive at low CCV, and weakly negative at high CCV. This is in agreement with prior theoretical and experimental studies showing that the Lorentz force can either marginally enhance or slightly degrade photovoltaic performance depending on whether the device is operating in a transport-limited or collection-limited regime [3, 5, 8].

Effect of the Carrier Collector Velocity on the Photovoltage of a Rear-Illuminated Cell under Different Magnetic Field Intensities

Case of a cell with a 100 μm base thickness

Figure 6 presents the trend of the photovoltage of a 100 μm -thick photovoltaic cell, rear-side illuminated, as a function of the carrier collection velocity at the p–n junction, in the presence of magnetic fields of varying intensity.

Figure 6: Photovoltage of a 100 μm PV cell Rear-side illuminated as a function of the recombination velocity for different values of the magnetic field B

Figure 6 shows that, regardless of the carrier collector velocity at the p–n junction (i.e., whether the operating point is close to short circuit or open circuit), the photovoltage decreases as the magnetic field intensity B increases. This trend can be explained by magnetic-field-induced modifications to carrier transport properties [5, 8, 10], increased bulk recombination losses [1,2,16,17], and possible rises in both series and shunt resistances [2,3]. The reduction in effective diffusion coefficient and diffusion length under the Lorentz force [5,6] contributes to lowering carrier collection efficiency, while resistive losses, linked to contact quality and leakage paths, further compress the photovoltage [2,4,7].

Case of a cell with a 300 μm base thickness

Figure 7 highlights the evolution of the photovoltage of a 300 μm -thick photovoltaic cell, rear-side illuminated, as a function of the carrier collection velocity at the p–n junction. This analysis is performed under the influence of magnetic fields of varying intensity.

Figure 7: Photovoltage of a 300 μm PV cell Rear-side illuminated as a function of the recombination velocity for different values of the magnetic field B

The analysis of the curves in Fig. 7 reveals a trend similar to that obtained for a base thickness of 100 μm , indicating that the dominant mechanisms influencing the photovoltage remain comparable between the two configurations. However, a reduction of approximately 76 mV in V_{ph} is observed compared to the values recorded for the 100 μm base.

This decrease can be explained by the longer optical path and carrier transit times in the thicker base, which increase the probability of bulk recombination before collection [1,2,16,17]. In particular, the additional diffusion distance, combined with non-negligible recombination velocities, reduces the quasi-Fermi level separation, leading to a lower photovoltage, as predicted by the analytical models of Sze and Ng [1] and Green [2].

Furthermore, the similarity in the curve shapes between the two base thicknesses confirms that, under these conditions, the influence of the magnetic field and the carrier collector velocity is governed primarily by carrier transport and recombination dynamics rather than by optical effects related to substrate thickness [3,5,8,10]. This finding is consistent with the results reported by Wang et al. [18] and Lee et al. [8], which show that the impact of a magnetic field on photovoltage is determined more by the prevailing transport regime, whether bulk-limited or collection-limited, than by the absorber thickness.

Effect of Recombination Velocity on the Photovoltage of a Solar Cell Illuminated on Both Sides under Magnetic Fields of Varying Intensities

Case of a cell with a 100 μm base thickness

Figure 8 presents the variation of the photovoltage of a 100 μm -thick photovoltaic cell, simultaneously illuminated on both the front and rear sides, as a function of the carrier collection velocity at the p–n junction, under magnetic fields of varying intensities.

Figure 8: Photovoltage of a 100 μm PV cell illuminated on both sides as a function of the recombination velocity for different values of the magnetic field B

The analysis of Fig. 8 shows that the magnetic field intensity has an overall negligible effect on the photovoltage for any value of the carrier collector velocity at the p–n junction. This apparent invariance can be explained by the compensation between two opposing effects:

- **Under front-side illumination**, the magnetic field tends to slightly reduce transport losses by altering carrier trajectories, which can induce a marginal increase in V_{ph} [3,8].
- **Under rear-side illumination**, the same magnetic field can enhance bulk losses (reducing both the diffusion length and diffusion coefficient), leading to a decrease in V_{ph} [1,2,16,17].

When the contributions of the two illumination modes are combined, these opposite effects partially cancel each other out, resulting in an overall very small variation in photovoltage regardless of the carrier collector velocity. This behavior is consistent with reports in the literature on bifacial cells under moderate magnetic fields [18,19,20], where the net response is determined by the balance between front-side and rear-side losses.

Case of a cell with a 300 μm base thickness

Figure 9 presents the variation of the photovoltage density of a 300 μm -thick photovoltaic cell, illuminated simultaneously on both the front and rear sides, as a function of the carrier collection velocity at the p–n junction. The analysis is performed under magnetic fields of varying intensities.

Figure 9: Photovoltage of a 300 μm PV cell illuminated on both sides as a function of the recombination velocity for different values of the magnetic field B

For the 300 μm base cell, the compensation observed in thinner cells between the front-side and rear-side illumination effects is not achieved. This is explained by the relatively weak contribution of rear-side illumination compared to front-side illumination for thicker bases. In such cells, the optical absorption and carrier generation remain strongly dominated by the front side, meaning that the behavior of V_{ph} under magnetic field influence is primarily determined by the front-side illumination regime.

In this configuration, the magnetic field’s impact on photovoltage follows the same qualitative trends as under front-side illumination: a marginal increase in V_{ph} for low carrier collector velocities, associated with a slight reduction in bulk recombination losses due to the Lorentz force [3,8], and a gradual decrease in V_{ph} at higher velocities, caused by the reduction in effective diffusion length and coefficient [1,2,16,17]. Because the rear-side generation is less significant in thicker cells, its opposing influence is insufficient to counterbalance the front-side effect, resulting in a net magnetic-field-induced variation in photovoltage.

This finding is consistent with theoretical models [1,2,16] and experimental results [3,8,17] showing that, in devices with thicker absorbers, the relative weight of rear-side contributions decreases, and magnetic field effects are dictated mainly by the illumination geometry that produces the highest carrier generation rate, here, the front surface.

Influence of Magnetic Field on the Photovoltage of a Solar Cell with Varying Thicknesses PV Cells Illuminated on the Front Side

The curves in Figures 10 and 11 illustrate the evolution of the photovoltage of a photovoltaic cell with varying base thicknesses (from 100 μm to 400 μm in 50 μm increments), front-side illuminated, as a function of the magnetic field intensity B, corresponding respectively to operating conditions near open-circuit and short-circuit.

Figure 10: Photovoltage as a function of the magnetic field for a front-illuminated PV cell with different base thicknesses under open-circuit conditions

Figure 11: Photovoltage as a function of the magnetic field for a front-illuminated PV cell with different base thicknesses under short-circuit conditions

More clearly than in Figures 4 and 5, Figure 10 shows that, in the open-circuit regime, the photovoltage V_{ph} increases with magnetic field intensity at a rate of approximately 10 mV per decade, regardless of the base thickness considered. This behavior, consistent across multiple thickness configurations, confirms that applying a moderate magnetic field can, under certain conditions, slightly improve the voltage performance of photovoltaic cells [3,8]. Such an effect has been reported in both experimental and simulation studies on the influence of magnetic fields on carrier transport in semiconductors [1,2,3,8]. In regimes where bulk recombination is not dominant, the Lorentz force can slightly modify minority-carrier trajectories, reducing diffusive losses and yielding a marginal V_{ph} enhancement. Similar observations have been made for bifacial devices under front-side or dual-face illumination [13, 17] where the improvement was attributed to a reduction in bulk recombination losses. The independence from base thickness suggests that, in this operating range, the magnetic field acts primarily on transport parameters such as the diffusion coefficient and diffusion length, rather than on optical path effects [2,8]. This is in agreement with [16] who showed that magnetic-field effects on performance are more closely tied to transport conditions than to absorber thickness, once the latter exceeds a few tens of micrometers.

In contrast, Figure 11, corresponding to short-circuit conditions, shows a clear and nearly linear decrease in V_{ph} as the magnetic field increases, for all base thicknesses investigated. This drop, from the open-circuit values down to lower voltages, reflects the dominance of carrier collection at high carrier-collector velocities, which enhances junction recombination and increases the effective dark saturation current J_0 [1,2,15]. The similar slopes observed across different thicknesses indicate that, under short-circuit conditions, the reduction in V_{ph} is driven more by recombination–transport interplay than by geometrical factors. This aligns with previous findings [3,8] showing that, in collection-limited regimes, the Lorentz force tends to lengthen carrier trajectories and thus increase recombination losses, leading to a measurable voltage drop.

PV Cells Illuminated on the Rear Side

Figures 12 and 13 illustrate the evolution of the photovoltage of a photovoltaic (PV) cell with varying base thicknesses (from 100 to 400 μm in 50 μm increments), illuminated on the rear side, as a function of the magnetic field B, under open-circuit and short-circuit conditions, respectively.

Figure 12: Photovoltage as a function of the magnetic field for a rear-illuminated PV cell with different base thicknesses under open-circuit conditions

Figure 13: Photovoltage as a function of the magnetic field for a rear-illuminated PV cell with different base thicknesses under short-circuit conditions

Figures 12 and 13 show a similar trend in the evolution of the photovoltage V_{ph} : in both cases, it decreases with increasing magnetic field intensity and with increasing base thickness. The drop from 0.32 V to 0.21 V for a thickness variation from 100 μm to 400 μm is consistent with the models of Sze & Ng [1] and Green [2], which explain that a thicker base increases carrier transit time and raises the probability of bulk recombination, thereby reducing quasi-Fermi level separation and, consequently, V_{ph} . Experimental and simulation works [3,4,6] also indicate that, beyond a certain thickness, bulk recombination losses dominate optical gains.

The slope analysis reveals in both figures a linear and uniform decrease in V_{ph} with the magnetic field, with slopes being comparable across all studied thicknesses. This suggests that the magnetic field effect, mainly the reduction of the diffusion coefficient and diffusion length due to the Lorentz force [4,6], acts proportionally, regardless of the optical path length. These observations agree with prior studies [3,4,6], which emphasize that the magnetic field impact is governed more by transport parameters than by purely geometrical effects.

The main difference between the two figures lies in the operating regime. Near open-circuit conditions (Figure 12), the photovoltage reduction with magnetic field remains moderate (around 10 mV per decade). In contrast, near short-circuit conditions (Figure 13), the absolute photovoltage values are lower (0.05 V to 0.20 V versus 0.19 V to 0.32 V for open-circuit), and the drop per decade exceeds 10 mV. This indicates a greater sensitivity of V_{ph} to recombination losses amplified by the magnetic field in a regime dominated by carrier collection [1,2,9]. In this regime, the increased carrier collector velocity enhances junction recombination, raises the effective dark saturation current J_0 , and accelerates the loss of photovoltage.

PV Cells Illuminated on Both Sides

Figures 14 and 15 show the variation of the photovoltage of a photovoltaic (PV) cell with different base thicknesses (from 100 to 400 μm in 50 μm increments), illuminated on both the front and rear sides, as a function of the magnetic field intensity, under open-circuit and short-circuit conditions, respectively.

Figure 14: Photovoltage as a function of the magnetic field for a bifacially illuminated PV cell with different base thicknesses under open-circuit conditions

Figure 15: Photovoltage as a function of the magnetic field for a bifacially illuminated PV cell with different base thicknesses under short-circuit conditions.

Figures 14 and 15 show that, under simultaneous illumination of the front and rear surfaces, the photovoltage V_{ph} varies with magnetic field intensity and base thickness following the same general trend as for front-side illumination alone. Despite the counterbalancing effect of rear-side illumination, which generally tends to mitigate the magnetic field's influence, the dominant contribution to V_{ph} remains that of the front surface, particularly for thicker bases where rear-side generation is limited by absorption and transport losses [1,2,19].

More clearly than in other configurations, Figure 14 (open-circuit regime) shows that V_{ph} increases with magnetic field intensity at a rate of about 10 mV per decade, regardless of the base thickness considered. This behavior, consistent across multiple thickness configurations, confirms that applying a moderate magnetic field can, under certain conditions, slightly improve the voltage performance of photovoltaic cells [4,10]. This effect has been reported in both experimental and simulation studies on the influence of magnetic fields on carrier transport in semiconductors [1,2,3,4,6,19]. In regimes where bulk recombination losses are not dominant, the Lorentz force can slightly alter minority-carrier trajectories, reducing diffusive losses and yielding a small improvement in V_{ph} . Similar observations have been made for bifacial devices [8,14] under front-side or dual-face illumination, where the improvement was attributed to a reduction in bulk recombination losses. The independence from base thickness suggests that, in this operating range, the magnetic field acts mainly on transport parameters such as the diffusion coefficient and diffusion length, rather than on optical path effects [2,4]. This is consistent with the conclusions of [16], who showed that the effect of a magnetic field on performance is more closely tied to transport conditions than to absorber thickness once the latter exceeds a few tens of micrometers.

Figure 15, corresponding to short-circuit conditions, on the other hand, reveals a clear and nearly linear decrease in V_{ph} as the magnetic field increases, for all base thicknesses studied. This drop, from the open-circuit values down to lower voltages, reflects the predominance of carrier collection at high carrier-collector velocities, which enhances junction recombination and increases the effective dark saturation current J_0 [1,2,8]. The comparable slopes observed for different thicknesses indicate that, in this regime, the reduction in V_{ph} results more from the recombination–transport interplay than from geometrical factors. These results confirm previous findings [3,4,6], showing that in collection-limited regimes, the Lorentz force tends to lengthen carrier trajectories and thereby increase recombination losses, leading to a measurable photovoltage drop.

Influence of Carrier Collection Velocity on the Photovoltage of a Solar Cell with Varying Thicknesses PV Cells Illuminated on the Front Side

Figure 16 highlights the variation of the photovoltage density of a photovoltaic (PV) cell with base thickness ranging from 100 to 400 μm in 50 μm increments, front-side illuminated, as a function of the carrier collection velocity at the p–n junction. The study is conducted under the influence of a constant magnetic field ($B = 1e - 4 T$).

Figure 16: Photovoltage as a function of carrier collection velocity for a front-side illuminated PV cell with different base thicknesses under a magnetic field

The analysis of Fig. 16 shows that the photovoltage V_{ph} remains almost identical for all base thicknesses across the entire range of CCV values considered. In the first plateau, corresponding to CCV values between 10 and $5e3$ cm/s, V_{ph} is essentially constant and close to its maximum. This regime corresponds to operation near open circuit, where the junction collects very few carriers, and photovoltage is mainly determined by the quasi-Fermi level splitting induced by strong carrier accumulation at the junction [1, 2, 19]. Under these conditions, both transport losses and magnetic field, induced perturbations are minimal, consistent with a bulk-dominated transport regime [7,8].

In the second plateau, CCV between $5e3$ and $1e7$ cm/s, V_{ph} decreases linearly and rapidly, tending toward very low values as the device approaches short-circuit operation. In this regime, the large CCV values favor rapid carrier extraction but also enhance recombination through increased junction current, thereby elevating the effective dark saturation current J_0 and reducing V_{ph} [2,4]. This trend is largely independent of base thickness, indicating that, under simultaneous illumination, the dominant effect is governed by junction recombination and transport dynamics rather than optical path length differences.

The observed base-thickness invariance aligns with findings from earlier studies on bifacial and monofacial crystalline silicon cells, where the simultaneous front/rear generation leads to a balanced carrier profile, making V_{ph} less sensitive to thickness-dependent absorption differences [3,6]. The slight magnetic-field-induced variations within each plateau are consistent with the Lorentz force effects described in [11,17,18], which can marginally modulate carrier mobility and diffusion length without altering the overall plateau behavior.

PV Cells Illuminated on the Rear Side

The effect of the carrier collection velocity at the p-n junction on the evolution of the photovoltage of a photovoltaic (PV) cell, with base thickness varying from 100 to 400 μm in 50 μm increments, rear-side illuminated, in the presence of a constant magnetic field ($B = 1e - 4 \text{ T}$), is illustrated in Figure 17.

Figure 17: Photovoltage as a function of carrier collection velocity for a rear-side illuminated PV cell with different base thicknesses under a magnetic field.

Figure 17 shows that, under a constant magnetic field, the photovoltage V_{ph} of a PV cell illuminated from the rear side is inversely proportional to the base thickness, due to the longer transport path and increased bulk recombination losses [1,2,19].

For all base thicknesses, V_{ph} remains almost constant when the CCV is between 10 and $5e3$ cm/s, corresponding to an operating regime near open circuit, where the quasi-Fermi level separation controls the voltage [4,7,8].

When the CCV exceeds $5e3$ cm/s, V_{ph} decreases rapidly and linearly, reflecting enhanced junction losses and a higher dark saturation current (J_0), which compresses the available voltage [2,6].

This behavior is consistent with earlier studies showing that, under rear-side illumination, the magnetic field effect remains limited because optical generation is weaker than for front-side illumination, and transport/recombination losses dominate [3,17,18].

PV Cells Illuminated on Both Sides

Figure 18 highlights the evolution of the photovoltage of various photovoltaic (PV) cells with base thicknesses ranging from 100 to 400 μm in 50 μm increments, illuminated simultaneously from both the front and rear sides, in the presence of a constant magnetic field of intensity $B = 1e - 3 \text{ T}$.

Figure 18: Photovoltage as a function of carrier collection velocity for a both sides illuminated PV cell with different base thicknesses under a magnetic field

For Figure 18, a similar behavior is observed to that seen under front-side illumination, with one notable difference: there is a slight decrease in photovoltage as the base thickness increases. This reduction can be attributed to the rear-side illumination contribution, which becomes weaker for thicker bases due to the longer optical path and enhanced bulk recombination losses. As a result, although the front-side behavior dominates, the diminished rear-side generation slightly lowers the total photovoltage for thicker cells.

Effect of Base Thickness on the Variation of Photovoltage in a Rear-Side Illuminated Solar Cell Under Short-Circuit Conditions

Figure 19 below shows the relative variation of the photogenerated voltage of a PV solar cell illuminated from the rear side as a function of its base thickness. This variation analysis is carried out under the influence of a carrier collector velocity at the p–n junction equal to $1e7$ cm/s.

Figure 19: Relative variation of the photogenerated voltage of a rear-side illuminated PV solar cell as a function of its base thickness:

Figure 19 illustrates the relative variation of the photovoltage of a photovoltaic (PV) cell, illuminated from the rear side, as a function of its base thickness, under the influence of a fixed CCV of $1e7$ cm/s. Here, the plotted values correspond to the change in V_{ph} induced by a one-decade increase in magnetic field intensity.

For thin bases (100 μm to 150 μm), the relative variation of V_{ph} is slightly positive, suggesting that moderate magnetic fields can, in this range, marginally enhance carrier collection near the junction while limiting bulk recombination losses [1,2,19]. Between 150 μm and 250 μm , the relative change remains nearly constant at about +3%, indicating a regime where transport parameters, diffusion length L and diffusion coefficient D , are the main controlling factors, with limited influence from the base geometry [7,8].

Beyond 250 μm , the relative variation becomes negative and decreases progressively up to 400 μm . This decline reflects the increased dominance of bulk recombination losses over any magnetic-field-induced transport benefits, as carriers generated far from the junction experience greater recombination and resistive voltage drops [4,6]. Under rear-side illumination, optical attenuation before carriers reach the junction further amplifies this effect, consistent with transport models for thick-base silicon cells [3,17,18].

These results confirm that, at high carrier collection velocities, the influence of the magnetic field on rear-illuminated cells is strongly modulated by the competition between reduced transport efficiency and increased

recombination losses, in agreement with previous studies on both polycrystalline and monocrystalline silicon devices [1,2,3,4,6,18,19].

CONCLUSION

This study demonstrates that the influence of an external magnetic field on the photovoltage of bifacial polycrystalline silicon PV cells is highly dependent on the operating regime, illumination configuration, and base thickness.

Under open-circuit conditions, moderate magnetic fields can marginally improve V_{ph} by reducing diffusive losses, whereas in short-circuit regimes they systematically degrade voltage through enhanced recombination. Rear-side and dual-face illumination reveal the interplay between front- and back-generated carriers, with compensation effects most evident in thin bases.

From a design perspective, the findings suggest that while moderate magnetic fields are unlikely to cause severe degradation in well-optimized devices, their effects must be considered in environments where fields in the $1e - 4$ to $1e - 3 T$ range are present. The results also underscore that optimizing base thickness remains critical for balancing optical absorption and transport losses, particularly under rear or dual-face illumination.

REFERENCES

- [1]. S. M. Sze and K. K. Ng, *Physics of Semiconductor Devices*, 3rd ed. Hoboken, NJ, USA: Wiley, 2006.
- [2]. M. A. Green, *Silicon Solar Cells: Advanced Principles & Practice*. Sydney, NSW, Australia: Centre for Photovoltaic Devices and Systems, Univ. of New South Wales, 1995.
- [3]. J. Nelson, *The Physics of Solar Cells*. London, U.K.: Imperial College Press, 2003.
- [4]. A. Cuevas, "The impact of recombination processes on solar cell efficiency," *Energy & Environmental Science*, 7, 3223–3231, 2014.
- [5]. A. B. Sproul, "Dimensionless solution of the equation describing the effect of surface recombination on carrier decay in semiconductors," *J. Appl. Phys.*, vol. 76, no. 5, pp. 2851–2854, 1994.
- [6]. D. K. Schroder, *Semiconductor Material and Device Characterization*, 3rd ed. Hoboken, NJ, USA: Wiley, 2006.
- [7]. Aberle, A. G. (2001). Overview on SiN surface passivation of crystalline silicon solar cells. *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells*, 65(1–4), 239–248. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0927-0248\(00\)00099-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0927-0248(00)00099-4)
- [8]. M Zoungrana and all, "The effect of magnetic field on the efficiency of a silicon solar cell under an intense light concentration" *Advances in Science and Technology Research Journal* Volume 11, Issue 2, June 2017, pages 133–138 DOI: 10.12913/22998624/69699
- [9]. H. Kim and al., "Magnetic field–resilient photovoltaic structures," *Solar RRL*, vol. 4, no. 10, 2020.
- [10]. P. A. Basore, "Extended spectral analysis of internal quantum efficiency: Novel approach to measuring base diffusion length," in *Proc. 23rd IEEE Photovoltaic Specialists Conference (PVSC)*, 1993, pp. 147–152.
- [11]. Dugas, J. (1994). 3D Modelling of a Reverse Cell Made with Improved Multicrystalline Silicon Wafers. *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells*, 32(1), 71-88. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0927-0248\(94\)90257-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/0927-0248(94)90257-7)
- [12]. A. Dieng and al., "Determination of the optimal base thickness of an n+–pp+ silicon solar cell under magnetic field," in *Proc. 24th Eur. Photovoltaic Solar Energy Conf.*, 2009.
- [13]. P. A. Basore, "Extended spectral analysis of internal quantum efficiency: Novel approach to measuring base diffusion length," in *Proc. 23rd IEEE Photovoltaic Specialists Conference (PVSC)*, 1993, pp. 147–152. DOI: 10.1109/PVSC.1993.347063
- [14]. Wang, H. B., Bagnall, D. M., Lu, J. P., & Wang, J. B. (2000). Effect of magnetic field on photovoltaic characteristics. *Solar Energy Materials & Solar Cells*, 63(2), 161–167. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0927-0248\(00\)00021-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0927-0248(00)00021-0)
- [15]. C. Thiaw and al., "Determination of the optimal base thickness of an n+–pp+ silicon solar cell under magnetic field," *J. Electromagn. Anal. Appl.*, vol. 12, no. 7, pp. 139–154, 2020 doi: 10.4236/jemaa.2020.127009.
- [16]. H. Fathabadi, "Effect of Magnetic Field on Silicon-Based Solar Cells" *Avril 2020 Chimie et physique des matériaux* 244(6):122684 DOI: 10.1016/j.matchemphys.2020.122684
- [17]. C. T. Sah and al., "Impact of base thickness on the performance of bifacial silicon solar cells," DOI: 10.1109/T-ED.1982.20797
- [18]. Erin M. Tonita and all « Étude du transport des porteurs dans les cellules solaires bifaciales à hétérojonction en silicium sous un éclairage à forte masse d'air » 2020, Pages : 0465 - 0469. DOI: 10.1109/PVSC45281.2020.9300663
- [19]. M. A. Green, *Solar Cells: Operating Principles, Technology and System Applications*, Prentice-Hall, 1982.
- [20]. Liu, S., Zhang, M., & Wang, X. (2019). Enhanced bifacial solar cell performance through 3D modeling. *Renewable Energy*, 135, 1427–1434. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2018.12.062>